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**A STUDY ON THE DECLINE OF CAREER-DRIVEN
BEHAVIOUR AMONG TODAY'S STUDENTS IN
COIMBATORE**

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the growing lack of career-driven behaviour among today's students. And seeks to understand the factors contributing to reduced ambition, goal clarity, and career preparedness. In recent years, noticeable changes have emerged in how students perceive education and career planning. The present study focuses on how it appears among students in Coimbatore. Recognizing the importance of these challenges, the study aims to examine the factors contributing to the decline in career-driven behaviour among students in Coimbatore. By analyzing students' attitudes, motivations, and perceptions, the study seeks to provide insights that may assist educational institutions in strengthening career guidance practices and encouraging students to engage more actively in career planning and long-term goal development.

KEYWORDS

Career-driven behaviour, Career planning, Student Motivation, Psychological barriers, Employability skills, Digital media influence.

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INTRODUCTION

Education has traditionally served as a foundation for professional development and long-term career stability. The modern educational environment reflects a growing concern regarding the decline in career-driven behaviour among students. Across educational institutions in the city, many students show reduced interest in structured career planning, skill development, and long-term professional goals. Compared to earlier generations, today's students increasingly display uncertainty, disengagement, and weakened motivation toward future-oriented career paths. In recent years, students in Coimbatore have shown a noticeable decline in career-driven behaviour. Extensive use of social media and online platforms has altered students' attention, priorities, and expectations, often encouraging short-term satisfaction over long-term career planning. Psychological factors further affect students' career motivation. Stress, academic pressure, fear of failure, indecision, and low confidence reduce students' ability to set clear career goals or engage actively in career exploration.

Limited career guidance, and inadequate exposure to real-world professional environments weaken students' understanding of career opportunities and skill requirements. The gap between academic learning and industry expectations makes it difficult for students to connect education with practical career outcomes.

The decline in career-driven behaviour does not result from a single cause but from a combination of social, psychological, and institutional influences. This has significant implications for the future workforce of Coimbatore.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Hasira Banu, & Sivasakthi Rajammal, T. (2024). "Career Decision-Making Process Among Higher Secondary Students", International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts. The study examines declining career-driven behaviour because of informational and psychological barriers in students' career decision-making processes. This study indicates that students with low self-awareness and inadequate career information demonstrate hesitation, delayed planning, and reduced commitment toward career goals.

2. Gowsalya, G., & Preetha, R. (2021). "Employability Skills and Career Engagement Among College Students", International Journal of Advanced Research. The study focuses on declining career engagement because of employability skill deficiencies. It concludes that insufficient institutional training and industry exposure further contribute to reduced initiative and career-driven behaviour.

3. Guichard, J. (2015). "Life-Long Self-Construction and Career Development", Journal of Vocational Behavior. It studies declining career-driven behaviour as fragmented and incoherent career narratives that prevent students from committing to structured career pathways. The study emphasizes that structured career guidance and narrative-building interventions are essential to foster clarity, purpose, and sustained engagement in career planning.

4. Tomlinson, M. (2017). "Forms of Graduate Capital and Career Outcomes", Journal of Education and Work. It studies declining career motivation to diminish trust in employability outcomes and perceived gaps between education and work opportunities. The study highlights the importance of career assurance programs, industry partnerships, and realistic career expectation management to enhance motivation.

OBJECTIVES

1. To explore the impact of technology and digital media consumption on students' career motivation.
2. To assess psychological barriers, including fear of failure, indecision, and lack of self-efficacy, affecting career planning.
3. To identify knowledge gaps and misconceptions about career opportunities among students.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The study is limited to students in Coimbatore and may not represent other regions.
2. A limited sample size may affect the generalizability of the findings.
3. Only selected factors influencing career-driven behaviour are considered.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology refers to the systematic and scientific procedure adopted to collect, analyse, and interpret data to achieve the objectives of the study. It explains the overall research design, sources of data, sampling techniques, tools used, and methods of data collection. The present study follows a descriptive research approach to analyze the factors contributing to the decline in career-driven behaviour among students in Coimbatore.

SAMPLE DESIGN

The sample design describes the selection of students in Coimbatore who are relevant to the study. Respondents were chosen based on their ability to provide information related to career motivation, awareness, and career planning behaviour, ensuring meaningful analysis of the research objectives.

SAMPLE SIZE

The study is based on approximately 120 students from various educational institutions in Coimbatore. The sample size was considered adequate to analyze students' career-driven behaviour and to meet the objectives of the study within the given time.

SOURCES OF DATA

Sources of data refer to the means through which information required for the study is obtained. The present study is based on both primary and secondary data.

PRIMARY DATA

Primary data were collected directly from students in Coimbatore using a structured questionnaire. The data gathered relates to career motivation, technology usage, psychological factors, perceptions of alternative careers, awareness of career opportunities, and views on job security.

SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data was collected from published resources available on reference websites. These data were used to provide background information and conceptual understanding related to career-driven behaviour, student motivation, career planning, and employment trends.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY

- Simple percentage
- Chi-square
- Ranking analysis
- Weighted mean

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1.SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

TABLE 1.1
DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE STUDY

Variable	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Below 18	14	11.67
	18-21	79	65.83
	22-25	16	13.33
	Above 25	11	9.17
	Total	120	100
Gender	Male	56	46.67
	Female	64	53.33
	Total	120	100
Current level of education	Diploma	26	21.67
	Undergraduate	76	63.33
	Postgraduate	18	15.0
	Total	120	100
Daily digital learning time	1-3 hours	56	46.67
	Less than 1 hour	28	23.33
	3-5 hours	24	20.0
	More than 5 hours	12	10.0
	Total	120	100
Primary study device	Smartphone	55	45.83
	Laptop/PC	28	23.33
	Tablet	26	21.67
	Multiple devices	11	9.17
	Total	120	100

INTERPRETATION

The table shows that the majority of respondents belong to the 18–21 age group (65.83%). Female respondents slightly dominate the sample (53.33%). Most of the respondents are Undergraduates (63.33%), followed by Diploma students (21.67%) and Postgraduates (15%). A large proportion of students spend 1–3 hours (46.67%) daily on digital learning, indicating moderate engagement. Smartphones are the primary study device for 45.83% of the

respondents, followed by Laptops/PCs (23.33%) and Tablets (21.67%), showing a strong preference for mobile-based learning among students.

2.CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

TABLE 2.1

Gender and Career related stress support

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.964 ^a	3	.047
Likelihood Ratio	8.128	3	.043
Linear-by-Linear Association	.002	1	.963
N of Valid Cases	120		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.80.			

INTERPRETATION

The p-value (0.047) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant relationship between gender and the type of support preferred to handle career-related stress. Gender influences the kind of support students prefer.

TABLE 2.2

Age and Misleading career guidance platforms

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.823 ^a	9	.096
Likelihood Ratio	15.542	9	.077
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.388	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	120		
a. 10 cells (62.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.47.			

INTERPRETATION

The p-value (0.096) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant relationship between age and the source of misleading career information. Age does not significantly influence students' perception of confusing career guidance platforms.

3. RANKING ANALYSIS

TABLE 3.1

Ranking factors reducing career focus

Factors reducing career focus	Frequency	Rank
Belief in Easy Online Money	53	I
Comparing Yourself on social media	50	II
Following Influencer Lifestyles	49	III
Distraction by Entertainment Apps	33	IV
Lack of Patience for Long-Term Growth	30	V
Choosing Flexibility over Stability	27	VI
No Clear Career Direction	26	VII
Less Interest in Traditional Careers	26	VIII

INTERPRETATION

The ranking analysis shows that the major factor reducing career focus is Belief in Easy Online Money rank first. This is followed by Comparing Yourself on social media rank second and Following Influencer Lifestyles rank third. Entertainment app distractions rank fourth. Factors like lack of patience, choosing flexibility, unclear direction, and less interest in traditional careers receive lower ranks. This shows that social media influence and unrealistic online success expectations are the primary reasons weakening students' career focus.

4. WEIGHTED MEAN ANALYSIS

Weighted Mean Formula

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum (f \times w)}{\sum f}$$

f = Frequency

w = Weight (Likert scale value: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5)

$\sum f$ = Total number of respondents

TABLE 4.1
Factors weakening career goals

Factors weakening career goals	N	Weighted Mean
Too many career options	120	3.82
Fear of choosing wrong career	120	3.65
Low self-confidence	120	3.37
No real industry exposure	120	3.29
Lack of knowledge on skills requirement	120	3.29
Fear of competition	120	3.39
Depending much on online advice	120	3.29
Unclear about long-term plans	120	3.48
Lack of career guidance	120	3.43

INTERPRETATION

This shows that “Too many career options” is the strongest factor weakening career goals. It is followed by Fear of choosing the wrong career and Unclear long-term plans. Other moderate factors include lack of career guidance, fear of competition, and low self-confidence. Overall, confusion, fear, and lack of clarity significantly affect students' career goals.

TABLE 4.2
Impact of Technology on careers

Impact of Technology on careers	N	Weighted Mean
Technology reducing career focus	120	3.78
Online success looks easy	120	3.54
Many options cause confusion	120	3.49
Digital content lowers confidence	120	3.43
Online trends pressure quick success	120	3.46
Technology distracts learning skills	120	3.53
Online career info confusing	120	3.44
Technology creates unrealistic goals	120	3.4

INTERPRETATION

The analysis reveals that students feel technology is reducing career focus. They also believe online success looks easy and that technology distracts learning skills. Online trends create

pressure for quick success, and digital information causes confusion. Overall, technology has a significant psychological and motivational impact on students' career development.

FINDINGS

- The majority 46.67% of the respondents spend 1–3 hours daily on digital media for learning.
- The majority 45.83% of the respondents use smartphones during study time.
- There is a significant association between gender and the type of support required to handle career-related stress ($p = 0.047 < 0.05$). Gender influences the preference for career support.
- There is no significant association between age and the source of confusing or misleading career information ($p = 0.096 > 0.05$). Age does not influence the perception of misleading information sources.
- The analysis shows that belief in easy online money and social media influence are the dominant factors affecting respondents. Digital trends have a stronger impact on career mindset than traditional career stability.
- The weighted mean scores show that respondents moderately agree that multiple career options and fear of making wrong decisions create confusion. Lack of proper guidance and clarity contributes to career uncertainty.
- The weighted mean values indicate that respondents agree technology influences their career perceptions. Digital platforms are seen as both informative and distracting, sometimes creating unrealistic expectations about success.

SUGGESTIONS

The study shows that students are deeply connected to digital platforms for learning and career information. Since many spend several hours online and use smartphones during study time, it is important to guide them on how to use these tools wisely. Colleges can organize simple workshops to help students understand how to identify trustworthy information and avoid being influenced by unrealistic success stories often seen on social media.

Many students feel confused because they are surrounded by too many career choices and are afraid of making the wrong decision. Some are also unsure about the skills required for different careers. To reduce this confusion, institutions should provide regular career counseling, skill-based training programs, and opportunities for internships. Practical exposure and real-world experiences can help students gain clarity and confidence about their future.

Students also value alumni interactions, which means connecting them with graduates and professionals can make career guidance more relatable and practical. Since support needs may differ, especially in handling career-related stress, colleges should offer friendly and accessible counseling services. Overall, by providing proper guidance, real exposure, and emotional support, institutions can help students make more confident, realistic, and carefully considered career choices.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the study shows that career-driven behaviour among students in Coimbatore is slowly going down, mainly because of digital influence, mental pressure, and a lack of clear direction. Students are always online and have access to tons of career information, but just having information doesn't mean they are planning their future in a focused, long-term way.

Social media plays a huge role here. The idea of easy online money, constantly comparing themselves with others, and getting attracted to quick success stories are shaping how students think about careers. At the same time, many of them feel confused about what skills they really need, scared of choosing the wrong path, and unsure about what the future holds. All this slowly affects their confidence and clarity.

So, the problem isn't that students don't have ambition. It's more about distraction, unrealistic expectations, and scattered thinking. Their career mindset today is influenced more by digital trends and short-term goals than by steady, practical, long-term career planning.

This shows the importance of helping students develop clarity and a more realistic, long-term approach towards their careers in today's transforming world.

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